

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE UNSUSPECTED ROLE OF MELANIN PIGMENTATION OF THE EGGSHELL IN THE GAS EXCHANGE

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Abstract

The principles of artificial egg incubation were established centuries ago. At that time, heat, moisture and air renewal of the incubation environment, well as the egg turning, were already taken into consideration, but the eggshell pigment had has been always menospreciate.

The avian eggshell forms the barrier between the internal and external environment of the egg. It protects the embryo mechanically against impacts and serves as a barrier against bacterial infection. The inner side of the shell serves as a source of calcium for the development of embryonic bones. An important feature of the eggshell is its porosity. The avian embryo respire by exchanging oxygen and carbon dioxide across the pores in the eggshell. The pores also provide escape route for water vapor.

AT the light of our finding of the unsuspected intrinsic property of eggshell pigment (melanin) to dissociate and re-form the water molecules, we must re-review the role of the physical agents of incubation, such as temperature, relative humidity, O₂ and CO₂ concentration, since they are variables that are largely determined by the recently discovered pigment function of the eggshell.

Keywords: hydrogen, eggshell, energy, melanin, pigment, sunlight, oxygen, water dissociation.

Introduction

In-ovo development is influenced by pre-incubation factors that affect the quality of embryonated eggs and incubation conditions themselves, and both may influence egg hatchability and chick quality, as well as bird survival, growth performance, and phenotype in the field.

There is evidence that it is the eggshell water vapor conductance (GH₂O) determines the precise amount of O₂, CO₂ and water vapor that is exchanged between the internal and external environment of the egg. Thus, diffusive conductance of gases, in and out of the egg, increases if pores are more numerous, wider and shorter. As shell porosity decreases, the amount of CO₂ that escapes across the shell is reduced.

It has been reported that eggshell conductance increases with egg weight since larger eggs have more porous shells. Furthermore, some researchers reported a wide variation in shell porosity between eggs of different hens. Typically, the pore numbers in domestic hen range between 7,000 and 17,000. Differences in eggshell conductance has been ascribed to differences in age of parent stock, as older parents produce eggs of higher shell conductance.

Other factors are ambient temperature, and feed composition. Thus, to create optimum gas exchange in the embryonic environment, suggested that the functional conductance of the eggshell must be considered along with the gaseous composition and barometric

pressure of the ambient fresh air, the incubator ventilation rate and the embryonic O₂ uptake melanin eggshell content, and amount of light.

The metabolic rate of the embryo increases during the second half of incubation and thus is the oxygen requirement. Theoretically, O₂ supply is limited by the eggshell water vapor conductance of the shell and other physiological characteristics of the embryo. The result is a plateau phase of O₂ input and CO₂ output. This phase is reached earlier in eggs with lower eggshell conductance (especially eggs from young breeders).

Air cell pO₂, just before pipping, increases with increasing conductance of the eggshell and the reverse is true for pCO₂. With increasing conductance of the shell, pipping by embryos is delayed. Hatchability has also been reported to be inversely related to eggshell conductance. Eggs with the lowest eggshell conductance achieve the highest hatchability irrespective of the age of the parent stock. The stage of embryonic mortality has been related to eggshell conductance; late embryonic mortality is higher in eggs with high eggshell conductance.

Water vapor conductance is one of the important factors that influence the embryonic gas exchange and development of the embryo. During embryonic growth, the gas exchange of the avian embryo is limited by the diffusion of gases through the pores of the eggshell. Few studies have carried out on the influence of genetic selection of eggshell characteristics, like eggshell conductance and even less about pigmentation. It has been

observed that eggs from older hens have higher eggshell water vapor conductance, this variation could have arisen from the difference of the breeder age and pigmentation degree of the eggshell.

Therefore, to make an ideal gas exchange during the embryonic development, the conductance of eggshell should be considered as a functional tool besides other factors like a gaseous composition, barometric pressure of the surrounding natural air, the hatchery ventilation rate, humidity and embryonic oxygen uptake and overall melanin content in the eggshell.

Changes in shell porosity have been seen among flocks of different ages. It has been found these changes are because of the number and cross-sectional area of the pores and not due to the thickness of the eggshell.

Eggshell water vapor conductance (GH_2O) also affects hatchability in broiler hatching eggs. So, when the flock age increase, weight of egg and yolk sac percentage of embryo increase, whereas the thickness of shell decreases. It was also reported that yolk sac percentage of embryos from smaller eggs was greater when compared to larger eggs of similar ages.

It was found that eggs obtained from older breeders possess higher water vapor conductance. There is a reduced hatchability and increased embryonic mortality with the advanced age of the breeder. Young flock hens produce thicker eggshells and light chicks due to a less exchange of gases and lower eggshell conductance than older flocks. GH_2O values shows an increment in the first half of the laying cycle, then becomes moderate and constant, and finally increased again at the end of the laying cycle. Eggs from 37 wk-old flock had higher water vapor conductance compared with eggs from 35-43 wk-old flocks.

With the increase of flock age, water vapor conductance also shows an increment in layer hens. The increased conductance facilitates oxygen uptake of the embryo during late period of incubation. Other research showed that increasing conductance rate could be the reason for high embryonic mortality.

Thereby, Eggshell quality such as conductance, thickness, and pore density are an important characteristic that affects the embryonic gas exchange and development of the embryo. The relationship between these parameters such as, eggshell conductance and flock age should be taken in consideration for debating their impacts on hatching output.

But there is a component that had gone unnoticed, and it is the degree of pigment pigmentation of the eggshell. And its role is subject to enormously importance due to the discovery of intrinsic property of melanin to dissociate and re-form the water molecule.

Melanin, a fundamental molecule of the eggshell

Nature only insists on important things, and the omnipresence of the pigment in eggshell is not an accident or mere relationship with the widely diffused idea that melanin is a simple solar filter or even a sunscreen.

As our finding about the unsuspected melanin's ability to transform light power into chemical energy by dissociation of water molecules has been gradually accepted.

Thereby, the control of factors as temperature, relative humidity, O_2 and CO_2 concentration, it has a new element that is a key regulator and that had gone unnoticed: the pigmentation of the shell. (Figure 1)

Figure 1) Diagram of inner current flows in the egg.

Comment

The evolution of the incubation process over the years is characterized by significant scientific and technological development, thereby is striking the lack of communications about the biological role of pigment in

the eggshell. Over the past 50 years, global annual meat production has almost quadrupled from 78 million tons in 1963 to 308 million tons in 2015, achieving an impressive growth from about 205 million tons to 319 million tons between 1995 and 2015.

To meet this high demand for poultry meat, hatcheries need to maximize chick production, and this entails not only the incubation of more fertile eggs. Today, hatcheries need to achieve high production efficiency in a sustainable manner, which, in our view, includes maximizing the hatchability of healthy chicks with high survival rates and the maximum expression of their genetic growth potential under any conditions in the field.

Scientific knowledge on incubation acquired over the years shows that the physical factors to which the eggs are subjected before and during incubation determine the production efficiency of hatcheries and poultry farms. Nevertheless, little is known about the effective participation of the integrated effects of physical factors of poultry during the different stages of production in ancient Egypt, eggs were incubated in mud-brick buildings (an “incubation house”) divided in incubation chambers like ovens separated by a central hallway and accessible through manholes. In the upper part of the egg chambers, there were shelves for burning, straw, dung, or charcoal to heat the eggs below. Vents in the roof allowed the smoke from the fires to escape and provided some light. In this primitive incubation system, the temperature within the incubation

chambers was managed by controlling fire intensity and opening the manholes, vents, and the hallway. Humidity was controlled by placing moistened jute on eggs, which were manually turned twice per day. Mechanical incubating was not invented until the year of 1749 by Reamur in Paris, France, and the first commercial incubator was manufactured by Hearson in 1881.

An incubator should be able to regulate factors, such as temperature and humidity, and to allow air renewal and egg turning, providing the perfect environmental conditions for embryonic development, aiming at achieving high hatchability of healthy chicks, which is directly correlated with the survival and performance of individual chicks in the field. But nature placed an element in the eggshell that acts as an incubator since the beginning of time: melanin.

And said pigment, as current incubators, is capable of incubating different numbers of eggs of different species of birds. Thereby, avian egg was provided, since beginning of time, with an automatic system controlling all the physical factors of incubation: environmental temperature set according to eggshell temperature determined by thermogenesis; air relative humidity and egg water loss previously determined; and air quality (O_2 and CO_2 levels). (Figure 2)

Figure 2) Water dissociation at the eggshell is a groundbreaking concept.

The eggshell does not participate passively in and allows exchanges between two separate environments, as determined by the interaction among temperature, relative humidity, ventilation, and egg turning during incubation, which are essential for the success of em-

bryonic and fetal development. To the previous concepts, thereby, from now on we would add the presence of pigment, the amount of light, and the unsuspected capacity of eggshell melanin to dissociate and reform the water molecule. Figure 3

Figure 3) Each light blue star represents water molecules dissociating and reforming inside the eggshell itself. Time that each melanin granule takes to dissociate the molecule of the water is around a trillionth of second.

The process of dissociation and reforming of water that occurs inside the pigment and therefore within the eggshell can be written as follows:

So, oxygen and water flows inside the egg are largely determined by this incessant flow of oxygen, water, hydrogen, and high energy electrons, since the process occurs incessantly, both day and night, providing the embryo the fundamental elements for its hatching. Figure 4

Figure 4) The discovery of intrinsic property of melanin to dissociate and reform water molecules, forces us to consider these processes simultaneously when analyzing the biology of the egg, since they are decisive from the very beginning of life. In the figure both were overlapped.

Conclusion

The belief that during physical exchanges between the egg and the external environment (egg and air of the incubator) include heat transfer and the exchange of O₂, CO₂ and water, the role of the eggshell is passive, must be changed.

The dissociation and re-form of the water that takes place inside the pigment contained in the cascaron, is a fundamental piece of the hatching of the embryo throughout the cycle. Hence, since it is expelled by the chicken, the egg has already impregnated in the shell, the necessary pigment to carry out the beginning and termination of the hatching process.

For instance, at high elevations, dry air is expected to increase water loss from the egg; selection to avoid desiccation might therefore be expected to favor reduced gas conductance by means of increased eggshell thickness (and melanin content) or reduced pore size.

This work can be considered an introduction to the subject, because it will also be necessary to consider, in one way or another, to the action of the melanin that is forming inside (progressively) the embryo cells.

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